

A Rare Case of Lymphangiomyomatosis in Sri Lanka

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Abstract

Lymphangiomyomatosis (LAM) is a rare disease, found approximately 1 in 1,000,000 in general population. LAM is characterized by progressive non-neoplastic proliferation of smooth muscle-like LAM cells resulting in destruction and cystic remodeling of lung parenchyma. Progressive dyspnoea, recurrent pneumothorax, chylothorax, cough, and hemoptysis are the usual manifestations of the disease. Demonstration of diffuse cysts in lung parenchyma in high resolution computerized tomography (HRCT) with typical clinical features can diagnose lymphangiomyomatosis without histology, which is necessary for uncertain cases. LAM almost exclusively occurs females of reproductive age group. However rare cases of LAM have been reported in children and postmenopausal females and even in men. We describe a rare case of lymphangiomyomatosis in a postmenopausal Sri Lankan woman.

Keywords- Lymphangiomyomatosis, pleural effusion, cystic lung diseases, mTOR inhibitors

Case report

A 56-year-old non smoking Sri Lankan woman presented to us with ten months history of progressive dyspnoea. She had noticed accompanying mild cough without hemoptysis, fever or constitutional symptoms.

Her background history revealed that she had been diagnosed to have sero-negative rheumatoid arthritis 6 years ago, for which she had received Methotrexate and Sulfasalazine for 3 years as disease modifying agents. However, she had discontinued them herself as her symptoms of arthritis remitted 3 years back. Additionally, she had undergone hysterectomy 8 years ago as a result of dysfunctional uterine bleeding.

A respiratory examination was suggestive of left sided moderate pleural effusion. This was confirmed by chest X-ray and ultrasound examination. Analysis of pleural fluid revealed turbid yellow color fluid containing 5.2 g/dL of protein, 30-40/ml white cells with 60% lymphocytes. Pleural fluid adenosine deaminase level was 17 IU/L, while triglyceride level was 19 mg/dL. Cultures for bacteria and tuberculosis, smear for acid-fast bacilli, and cytology for malignant cells were unremarkable. A pleural biopsy obtained by video-assisted thoracoscopic surgery revealed only non-specific finding of a perivascular collection of lymphocytes and plasma cells.

Her sedimentation rate was elevated to 98 mm, but C-reactive protein was within normal range. Additionally, full blood count, liver profile, renal profile, antinuclear antibody, anti-ds DNA, HIV antibodies, sputum for acid fast bacilli, and Mantoux test did not show significant abnormality. The spirometric assessment noted severe restrictive pattern. However diffusion capacity for carbon monoxide was within normal limits.

HRCT chest identified 1-12 mm size diffuse parenchymal cysts bilaterally. There was no lymphadenopathy, pulmonary nodules or other interstitial changes. Surgical lung biopsy revealed nonspecific focal lymphoid aggregates with scattered lymphocytes, plasma cells and multinucleated giant cells without granuloma in pleura again. However, lung tissue was not present in the sample for histological analysis.

Repeat lung biopsy was not attempted due to high surgical risk due to poor pulmonary reserve and recent acute coronary syndrome. The diagnosis of lymphangiomyomatosis was made according to clinical and radiological features.

She deteriorated gradually both clinically and in lung functions in spite of supportive treatment. She was commenced on Everolimus as an attempt to retard the disease progression according to recent evidence.

Discussion

Lymphangiomyomatosis is an extremely rare disease almost exclusively found in women of childbearing age group.(1) However, rare cases of LAM has been diagnosed before menarche and after menopause and also in males.(2)

The exact etiology is yet unknown.(3) Although LAM is considered to be a sporadic disease, some cases occur in association with tuberous sclerosis, an autosomal dominant neurocutaneous syndrome. The disease occurs as a result of the abnormal non-neoplastic proliferation of smooth muscle like LAM cells.(3)

The lung is the dominant organ affected in LAM. Progressive dyspnoea and recurrent pneumothorax are the most common presenting symptoms. A cough, hemoptysis, chylothorax, and chest pain are also commonly mentioned (1, 2). Chylous ascitis, chylopericardium, lymphoedema of extremities, mediastinal and intraabdominal lymphadenopathy, cystic lymphatic masses are known as lymphangiomyomas, and benign tumors known as angiomyolipomas are the other recognized complications of LAM.(1,2)

Our patient presented with progressive dyspnoea for several months and diagnosed to have a left sided pleural effusion. As she was a case of rheumatoid arthritis, who had received immunosuppressive treatment, rheumatoid arthritis associated lung disease, chronic infections, and malignancy has to be considered as the initial differential diagnosis. However, HRCT chest showed multiple cystic lesions and cystic lung diseases were suspected. Pulmonary Langerhan's cells histiocytosis (PLCH), LAM and lymphocytic interstitial pneumonia were the major differential diagnosis. Our patient had diffusely distributed cysts in contrast to PLCH, where middle and upper lobes are preferentially affected.

Pleural effusion, in this case, was the exudative type, but not suggestive of chylothorax as typically expected in LAM. As our patient presented at postmenopausal age, with additional compounding factors like history of rheumatoid arthritis and non-chylous pleural effusion, histological confirmation was required. However, two attempts to obtain lung tissue for histological evaluation were failed, and further attempts were not made due to high surgical risk. Considering the clinical and radiological features, the diagnosis was made as LAM.

The therapeutic options for LAM were limited until recently. Hormonal modulation with anti-oestrogen therapy, oopherectomy and progesterone was the main mode of treatment in addition to supportive treatment for complications. Advanced cases with respiratory failure were managed with a lung transplant.(1,2,3) Recent advances in research on cell biology have revealed multiple possible target therapy for LAM. Sirolimus, a mechanistic target of rapamycin (mTOR) inhibitor drug, has been recently investigated in a randomized control trial and shown benefit in improving symptoms, lung function tests and quality of life.(4) Another mTOR inhibitor, Everolimus has been shown promising effects on lung functions in a phase II trial (5).

Our patient was commenced on Everolimus as Sirolimus was not available, due to progressive deterioration of her condition and currently awaiting the assessment of response.

Conclusion

LAM is an important differential diagnosis for cystic lung diseases. Though typically occurs in reproductive age group females, cases are reported in postmenopausal women too. It can be diagnosed by HRCT alone in typical cases, but histological confirmation warranted in others. Recent advances in molecular studies have gained new hope for potential targeted therapy such as mTOR inhibitors for LAM.

List of abbreviations

HRCT- High resolution computered tomography-

LAM- Lymphangioliomyomatosis

mTOR- mechanistic target of rapamycin

PLCH- Pulmonary Langerhan's cells histiocytosis

Consent

Written informed consent was obtained from the patient for publication of this case report and accompanying images. A copy of the written consent is available for review by the Editor-in-Chief of this journal

Competing interest

The authors declare that they have no competing interest.

Authors' contribution

DM and SN made the clinical diagnosis and supervised the manuscript drafting. ARB and SS drafted the first manuscript, reviewed the literature and involved in direct management of the patient. DM supervised the manuscript drafting. RMDHMR Assist the case finding information and writing. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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References

- i. Sullivan EJ. Lymphangioliomyomatosis. *Chest* 1998; 114:1689-1703
- ii. Johnson SR. Lymphangioliomyomatosis. *Eur Respir J* 2006; 27: 1056–1065 DOI: 10.1183/09031936.06.00113303
- iii. Mavroudi M, Zarogoulidis P, Katsikogiannis N, Tsakiridis K, Huang H, Sakkas A, et al. Lymphangioliomyomatosis: current and future. *J Thorac Dis* 2013;5(1):74-79 DOI: 10.3978/j.issn.2072-1439.2013.01.03
- iv. McCormack FX, Inoue Y, Moss J, Singer LG, Strange C, Nakata K, et al. Efficacy and Safety of Sirolimus in Lymphangioliomyomatosis. *N Eng J Med* 2011;364:1595-1606
- v. Hilary Goldberg J, Harari S, Cottin V, Rosas IO, Peters E, Biswal S, et al. Everolimus for the treatment of lymphangioliomyomatosis: a phase II study. *Eur Respir J* 2015 Sep; 46(3):783-794 DOI: 10.1183/09031936.00210714

Chest Radiograph Showing left Sided Pleural Effusion

HRCT chest showing multiple cystic lesions

